

ISic1232

I.Sicily inscription 1232

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

stele

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,
inventory 8731

Physical Description

The upper portion of a marble stele, of which the lower part is wholly lost. Minor damage to the upper edge, and of the surviving portion the lower right corner is broken. The stele has a moulding framing the text, parallel with the vertical sides, and in a rounded semi-circle at the top; what may be two acroteria-like 'wings' or 'horns' are more lightly incised upper left and upper right.

Dimensions

Height 46.8 cm

Width 38.3 cm

Depth 8 cm

Layout

Text is enclosed within a relief-carved moulding, and centred. The first three lines are smaller, compressed within the semi-circular top of the frame/moulding; the rest of the text is of uniform size.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Text of fragment 'a' after IGPalermo and photograph; text of fragment 'b' after Gualtherus and Kaibel, and requiring further revision

Kaibel: ἔχει[ν ἐ]πόθησεν

Gualtherus: ΛΥΓΡΟΙC Μ . . . | ΜΑΤΑ; Torremuzza et al.: ὄμ- | ματα

Gualtherus: ΜΥΡΟΜΕΝC . . ; Torremuzza: μυρομένη

Translation

Commentary

This stone has a complicated publication history, due to a combination of reproduction from earlier scholars and the various vicissitudes of the two attested fragments, of which the upper (a) was lost and then rediscovered by A. Gallo, and still survives; while the lower, (b) was seemingly lost, then rediscovered by Gualtherus, and subsequently lost again (and is still lost). Torremuzza resolved the fundamental problems of the text's history, which were then partly obscured again by Kaibel, and effectively resumed by Manni Piraino. However, the presentation of the text of (b), for which the surviving tradition rests in the transcription made by Gualtherus, is not entirely reliable at any point in the subsequent tradition, with minor points of arbitrary alteration already in the text of Torremuzza. The tendency of editors to present the text of the second fragment only according to the prosody of the verses, rather than the layout of the text on the stone increases the confusion.

Gualtherus reported two texts in nos. 22 and 28 of the Messina edition, both derived from the manuscript of Alberto Piccoli, and at the time described as lost. No. 28 is lines 1-3 of fragment (a), presented as a distinct funerary inscription; no.22 is lines 4ff of frag (a) together with a version of the text of frag (b). Subsequently, Gualtherus actually saw fragment (b) and presented a better text of this in the addenda to the Messina edition, at p.101 no.7. Torremuzza, in turn, was made aware of the entirety of the text of fragment (a), when it was found by Andrea Gallo who sent him a transcription. This enabled Torremuzza to recognise that Gualtherus' nos. 28 in fact stands as the first three lines before the text of Gualtherus' no. 22, and that the latter part of no.22 should be superseded by the version recorded by Gualtherus as p.101 no.7. The text of fragment (a) is secure, and the stone, previously in Messina and then the museum of S. Martino delle Scale (Monreale), is now in Palermo Museum; a gap of uncertain length follows line 11 of fragment (a); the text then resumes, on the basis of the transcription by Gualtherus (p.101 no.7), which has been variously amended by subsequent scholars. As Manni Piraino notes, Kaibel wrongly attributed the entire text as presented by Torremuzza to A. Gallo.

The text consists of a brief record of the dedicant, Aurelius Eutyches, followed by the typical abbreviated dedication to the spirits of the underworld and then a verse epigram recording the Cyzicene youths, drowned in a shipwreck, whom he buried. The stele itself, and its lettering is finely carved. On the basis of the dimensions of fragment (a), it is likely that the stele as a whole was approximately 1 metre tall.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491450

EDCS 39101597

PHI 140717

PHI 175622

Bibliography

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